

FROM LEADERSHIP SHARING TO WELL-BEING: WHY TASK INTERDEPENDENCE MATTERS

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Abstract

It is a well-established fact that shared leadership plays a crucial role in achieving various organizational outcomes including organizational commitment. However, the role played by task interdependence in this association needs to be explored. For enhancing productivity for organizational outcomes, the impact of this interaction with employee wellbeing must also be studied. Thus, the aim of this research was to study the impact of shared leadership on organizational commitment and wellbeing, with mediating role of psychological capital and moderating role of task interdependence. The sample of this study was Pakistani Nongovernmental Organizations (NGO's). Convenience sampling technique was used for data collection from 290 individuals. Data was collected online in google forms by contacting potential participants through email. Participants filled the questionnaires in google forms anonymously. After cleaning, data was transferred to Statistical Package for Social Sciences-20 (SPSS-20) and Mplus 7.11. Along with descriptive statistics and correlational analysis in SPSS-20), Full Structural equation modeling (SEM) was performed in Mplus. Correlation analyses indicated significant relationship between shared leadership, psychological capital, task interdependence, organizational commitment and wellbeing. The final SEM model indicated that psychological capital mediated the relationship of shared leadership with organization commitment and wellbeing although the path from shared leadership to psychological capital was insignificant. Task interdependence served as a significant moderator in SEM. The study results suggests that task interdependence is an important factor in understanding the influence shared leadership will have on organizational commitment and employee wellbeing. The results are discussed in the thesis with reference to the existing literature along with this study's limitation and implications.

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a dynamic process which inspires and encourages people to achieve the particular goal

(Frankel, 2019). It is a soft skill that will not dictate what to do, but empowers how to do in a given

situation (Feldman, 2018). There is no particular form of leadership that can be said to be more suitable for all scenarios, as a leader's effectiveness relies on the opportunity to change a leadership style as per the situation (Caceres, 2019). For projects, an efficient leadership style is essential because the specific time and diverse team make them less dedicated and involved, resulting in poor management, dispute and poor communication (Zhang, Cao & Wang, 2018). Project leadership is a mixture of leadership and management, where the attention is on completing results as a planner and the emphasis is on establishing, leading and motivating as a leader (Hassan et al., 2016; Pretorius, Steyn & Bon-Bernard, 2018).

Recently, project-based organizations have gained growing attention as an evolving organizational method to incorporate unique rational properties and expertise (Popaitoon & Siengthai, 2014). Project based organizations mostly deal with projects where people from diverse professional backgrounds with various skills prefer to work together to accomplish common goals for limited time (Kwak, Sadatsafavi, Walewski & Williams, 2015). For this diverse professional background combination, a style of leadership must incorporate sharing of the leadership power and empower the project team members; and for this empowerment, the importance of shared leadership is well established (D'Innocenzo, Mathieu & Kukenberger, 2014). Research has indicated that shared leadership is a state of shared factors embedded in team member ties and it can greatly boost team efficiency as well as organizational efficiency (Wang, 2013). Individuals with shared leadership will gain freedom as well as self-control from the dedicated leader or from the team's decision. Team members may also become more accountable for the decision-making process (Mehmood et al., 2024; Scott-Young 2019).

Projects are a temporary endeavor with limited time and budget so the wellbeing of team members is important. As far as wellbeing is concerned, it is clearly described as recognition of the different emotional levels of satisfaction, employee state of mind and personal growth Warr et al., 2006). Previous research has found that both emotional wellbeing and behavioural wellbeing are significant as a way of maintaining stability in good and bad

circumstances and preserving feelings of achievement (Schimmack et al., 2002). Research has demonstrated a positive relation in which shared leadership enhanced wellbeing and organizational commitment. Furthermore, it creates a positive relation between leader and team members (Kim et al., 2017).

Projects are temporary endeavors with a specific start and specific end time, and each project has unique characteristics, in project-based organizations, the working climate is diverse. This dynamic and complex nature of projects put extra pressure on team members, such as task pressure, unclear expectations and requirements for various positions. In some situation project base organizations have problems coping with the job and emotional situation of the team members which can create the extra pressure. Such pressure will increase well-being concerns of the team and these problems should be addressed. While handling the projects the project manager needs to share the responsibilities and leadership power with team members. With shared leadership, project team feel sense of responsibility and ownership with the project work, senses of ownership also create the strong relationship between project team and the organization, which creates a satisfactory work environment for the project team, and affects team performance (Robert, 2016). With shared leadership, the power of leadership is transferred with the project team which empower team members for knowledge sharing, and there is a strong coordination towards all activities related to team goal, at the end all factors affect the project. This particular research aims at exploring the role of shared leadership on employee's wellbeing and organizational commitment. *Visa-vis*, it intends to check the mediating role of psychological capital among shared leadership, wellbeing and organizational commitment. Furthermore, it investigates contingent role of task interdependence between shared leadership and psychological capital.

Literature Review

Shared leadership and Organizational Commitment

Shared leadership was addressed implicitly between 1950 -1960. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, further comprehensive studies began (Weiss 1994). It has three major characteristics; (1) Leadership is a universal characteristic of the relationship between individuals in a team, (2) there are no clear limits to

leadership, and (3) for all team members, leadership activities are shared (Bolden et al., 2009). Such shared leadership qualities will guarantee that the company is still diverse, systematic and engaging. As far as organizational commitment is concerned, it refers to the essence of the relationship of the team to the organization, identification of the team and participation in a given organization (Shahnawaz & Jafri, 2009). It reflects the decision of the team member to remain or leave the company (Meyer et al., 1993).

Research that has explored the correlation between leadership patterns and organizational commitment indicated that sharing of leadership and resources not only increases sense of ownership but also enhances organizational commitment (Raub & Robert, 2013). Depending on this framework, shared leadership is often believed to have a positive effect on organizational commitment, in projects, shared leadership with team members increases the organizational commitment (Necati, 2020). The association between shared leadership and organizational commitment is specifically explored in this research. So, the first hypothesis of the study pursues that:

H1: Shared leadership has a significant impact on organizational commitment.

Shared Leadership and Wellbeing

As stated earlier, one of most studied subjects of organizational culture is the existence and influence of leadership. According to literature organizational leadership have strong impact on team wellbeing (Kelloway & Barling, 2010). The action of manager has a significant impact on wellbeing of workers (Gilbreath et. al., 2004). There have been important consequences for studying human wellbeing with the introduction of positive psychology (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). Wellbeing and positive psychology have strong impact on workplace and individual psychological health (Fullagar & Kelloway, 2012). Shared Leadership creates good psychological health and positive feelings, stimulating more innovative, dynamic and productive thinking patterns. This enhances the intrinsic motivation of the team members, which offers a theoretical structure that describes the correlation of pleasant emotional states with productivity of an individual through

shared leadership (Fredrickson's, 2001). So, according to previous studies, it is hypothesized that:

H2: Shared leadership has a significant impact on wellbeing.

Psychological capital as mediator between shared leadership and organizational commitment

The connection between leadership and psychological capital is based on Bandura's agentic theory (2006), which argues that leadership plays a significant role in collective interaction, shared leaders evaluate the internal and external information and communicate with their team members (Walumbwa et al., 2011). When leadership and other members accept the productive ideas of the colleagues, team members feel more empowerment in a shared environment (Kirkman & Rosen, 1999). In addition, shared leadership promotes shared group environment that embraces team members with mutual support and encouragement to express their views in terms of group. The trust of team members in their leader is an important psychological resource that enhances their resilience (Chi-Min Wua, Tso-Jen Chen, 2018). So, based on these arguments shared leadership has a strong relation with elements of psychological capital (self-efficacy, hope, optimism and resilience), also having impact on organizational commitment.

According to the available research evidence, Psychological capital has a positive influence on organizational commitment. (Luthans, Norman, Avolio & Avey, 2008; Youssef & Luthans, 2007). For instance, Sinha, Talwar and Rajpal, (2002) argue that organizational commitment is associated with self-efficacy, hope and optimism. Buys and Rothmann (2010) identified a strong association between work involvement and organizational commitment. They concluded that team members who are involved in work have a strong social role and effective contribution. Jung and Yoon (2015), showed that there is an optimistic relationship between psychological capital and organizational commitment. So, according to previous literature, it is hypothesized that:

H3: Psychological capital significantly mediates the relationship between shared leadership and organizational commitment

Psychological capital as mediator between shared leadership and wellbeing

Research has conceptualized the concept of wellbeing in various manners. From a physiological point of view, wellbeing is the mechanism in which people escape suffering and distress in terms of the accomplishment of enjoyment. In general, wellbeing is characterized as an "individual's psychological health" that people experience typically including positive behaviors and emotions (Rafi et al., 2024; Ryan & Deci, 2001).

Since, psychological capital completely covers intellectual capital "What you know?" and have direct concern with "who are you?", it has been one of the factors that enhance positive psychological responses to stressful circumstances (Luthans et al., 2006; Luthans et al., 2007). The concept of psychological capital argues that many of the psychological structures are used as measures of a larger central framework. Luthans et al., (2008) have described that team with higher psychological capital have psychological tools which improve positive workplace behavior, so psychological capital has direct effect on wellbeing. Controlling workers' personal and work-related energy creates anxiety and leads to internal weakness, depression and disturbances of wellbeing. Elements of psychological capital like self-efficacy, hope and optimism tend to buffer the gateway to stress and anxiety. Avey and colleagues (2009) argued that psychological capital has a negative association with stress and anxiety. In another study, the positive association between psychological capital and wellbeing were demonstrated (Avey et al., 2010).

Psychological capital has not only been identified as positive contributor to organizations commitment and employee wellbeing, its path of operating as mediating factor has also been identified in several reach studies. For instance, Park, Kim, Yoon and Jo (2017) and Wu and Chen (2018) have provided evidence for mediating role of psychological capital in association of shared leadership with organizational commitment and psychological wellbeing. Currently there is limited research that shows the mediating role of psychological capital. Thus, in order to clarify and fill this gap the role of psychological capital in this research has hypothesized.

H4: Psychological capital significantly mediates the relationship between shared leadership and wellbeing.

Moderating Role of Task Interdependencies

The hierarchical work model provides new possibilities in terms of mobility and job structure, but team members who work together from different places rely on one another (Jimenez, 2017). Projects are typically structured; different tasks require different skills, and these tasks are highly independent to each other. This work connectivity is defined as task interdependence (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006; Kiggundu, 1983). Empirically, interdependence of tasks is significantly correlated with factors like shared influence (Molleman, De Jong & Van der Vegt 2007) and can thus influence shared leadership's association with other factors like psychological capital. In addition, interdependent team members make each other's jobs easier, they communicate more and trust each other to achieve shared goals (Liao, 2017). So, employees having high task interdependence are more vigilant as compared to other team members (Van De Vliert, Van Der Vegt & Emans, 2000).

However, it must be kept in mind that communication between team members does not automatically apply to the leader. A team having high task interdependence needs different leadership as compared to a team having low interdependence (Hinds & McGrath, 2006). Teams having high task interdependence are less dependent on leader's input (Gray & Meister, 2004). Thus, based upon discussion of literature in this section it can be discerned that there is a need to study the role of task interdependence as a moderator.

H5: Task interdependence moderates the relationship between shared leadership and psychological capital.

Research Methodology

The cross-relational analysis was followed in this research. A cross sectional online survey was conducted from 13/07/2020 to 09/08/2020. Which explore the impact of shared leadership on wellbeing and organizational commitment with mediating role of psychological capital and moderating role of task interdependence. The unit of analysis were employees of NGOs working in Pakistan. The project managers, who have power of leadership, and this leadership have strong impact on team members which affect the commitment level and wellbeing of the team. The key

source of competitive advantage for Pakistan are project-based organizations. NGO's from all over Pakistan were approached for this research. Team members of different projects are directly involved in this research by completing the questionnaire survey. Convenience sampling has been used for the current study and is used in the non-probability sampling. That will accurately reflect the true image of the entire population in explaining the impact of shared leadership on organizational commitment and wellbeing. Respondents have been told that their data will be kept confidential and will be used for academic research. By maintaining the anonymity of their responses and names, they were asked to respond to the questionnaires as correctly as possible so that the respondents could not fail to fill in the survey confidently. Nearly 500 questionnaires were provided to employees for data collection, and 300 detailed answers were eventually obtained. This analysis consists of a closed-ended questionnaire from various sources, which was used to test variables. The questionnaires with six sections in this sample were

answered by team members as respondents: demographics variables (gender, age, qualification and current position), Shared Leadership, Organizational Commitment, Wellbeing, Psychological Capital and Task interdependence. In this study 5 and 6 point-Likert scale was used to tap the responses.

Data Analysis

In this section, results of the study are presented. Along with descriptive results, Structural Equation Model to test the study model is presented in this chapter. The following section describes the sample characteristics of the study.

Sample Characteristics

The demographic variables used in this study are, gender, age, qualification and work experience of employees working with Pakistani NGO's. The detailed characteristics of demographic variables given below in table.

Table 1 Demographic Variables (N=290)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	179	61.7
Female	110	37.9
Transgender	01	0.3
Age in years		
14-19	17	5.9
20-29	114	39.3
30-39	83	28.6
40-49	49	16.9
50-69	27	9.3

Qualification

Matric	4	1.4
Inter	16	5.5
Bachelors/Masters	209	72.1
MS/PhD	61	21.0

Work Experience in years

0-5	123	42.4
6-10	61	21
11-15	48	16.6
16-20	26	9
21-25	14	4.8
26-45	18	6.1

Age has 33.34 mean, 31 median, 27 mode and 10.506 SD. Skewness and Kurtosis value of age are 0.69 and .044 respectively. Figure 4.1 present distribution of age with superimposed normal curve.

Age was categorized into categories in accordance with the decade of life in which participants were.

Data Normality

Table 2 Data Normality (N=290)

Scale	N	M	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Shared Leadership	10	37.45	7.43	-0.807	0.841
Organizational Commitment	08	28.26	5.55	-0.497	0.853

Wellbeing	05	16.26	4.92	-0.763	0.581
Psychological Capital	12	56.42	8.49	-1.275	3.333
Task Interdependence	05	19.75	3.03	-0.945	3.025

N= Total number of items, M= Mean score, SD= Standard Deviation, α = Cronbach’s alpha reliability

The value of cronbach’s alpha of all variables is more than 0.7, which shows good reliability of all scales used in this study.

Table .1: Instrument Reliability

Variables	Instrument	Cronbach Alpha	Items
Shared Leadership	(Carson et al. 2007)	0.91	10
Psychological Capital	(Luthan. 2007)	0.88	12
Organizational Commitment	(Meyer 1991)	0.81	08
Wellbeing	(Christian 2015)	0.84	05
Task Interdependence	(Pearce 1991)	0.77	05

Correlations

The following table presents the correlation between study variables.

Table 4.4 Correlations

Scale	1	2	3	4	5
Shared Leadership	-	0.45**	0.39**	0.39**	0.37**

Organizational Commitment	-	0.35**	0.28**	0.29**
Wellbeing	-		0.54**	0.42**
Psychological Capital			-	0.46**
Task Interdependence				-

** . Significant correlation at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Shared leadership has a significant and positive relationship with organizational commitment ($r = 0.45, p = 0.00$), wellbeing ($r = 0.39, p = 0.00$) and psychological capital ($r = 0.39, p = 0.00$).

Task Interdependence is positively and significantly related with shared leadership ($r = 0.37, p = 0.00$), organizational commitment ($r = 0.29, p = 0.00$), wellbeing ($r = 0.42, p = 0.00$) and psychological capital ($r = 0.46, p = 0.00$). Psychological Capital is significantly positively associated with organizational commitment ($r = 0.28, p = 0.00$) & wellbeing ($r = 0.54, p = 0.00$).

Structural Equation modelling (SEM)

For testing the hypothesized relationships figure 4.17, structural equation modelling was performed in two steps, as per recommendations of Sardeshmukh & Vandenberg (2017).

In step 1, full structural equation modelling was performed but with mediating pathways only. Task interdependence was entered only as a predictor as shown in the following figure 4.18 Sardeshmukh & Vandenberg (2017). As per literature review, this model was tested for partial mediation of Psychological capital.

STEP 1: Structural Model 1 with Psychological capital as mediator and Task interdependence as predictor.

The χ^2 value of the model was 1081.116 with RMSEA 0.04 (C.I = 0.03 - 0.05) and CFI 0.90 which indicated good fit to data. Number of free parameters was 133. The AIC value of this model was AIC 28195.22.

In this model shared leadership had direct influence on organizational commitment (0.53, $p = 0.00$) and wellbeing (0.23, $p = 0.01$). Results also indicated that psychological capital mediates this relationship of shared leadership with organizational commitment and wellbeing. The mediating pathway indicated that increase in shared leadership led to increased psychological capital (0.14, $p = 0.08$), though it is statistically insignificant, and then this increased psychological capital statistically significantly predicted increase in organizational commitment (0.50, $p = 0.00$) and enhanced wellbeing (0.82, $p = 0.00$). The model also indicated that task interdependence predicted psychological capital significantly positively (0.83, $p = 0.00$).

Figure 4.20 shows a diagrammatic presentation of the model 1.

Figure 4.20

Note: * = $p < 0.05$

STEP 2: Structural Model 2 with Psychological capital as mediator and Task interdependence as predictor and moderator

The AIC value of the model was 28181.69 and number of free parameters in this model was 134. According to Burnham & Anderson (2002) the difference of AIC can be calculated as per the following formula and the AIC (AIC_i - AIC_{min}), (28195.22 - 28181.69 = 13.53). The difference of M1 and M2 was 13.53, which shows good fitting model. In this model shared leadership had direct influence on organizational commitment (0.54, $p = 0.00$) and wellbeing (0.23, $p = 0.01$). Results also indicated that psychological capital mediates this relationship of shared leadership with organizational commitment

and wellbeing. The mediating pathway indicated that increase in shared leadership led to increased psychological capital (0.12, $p = 0.09$), though it is statistically insignificant, and then this increased psychological capital statistically significantly predicted increase in organizational commitment (0.50, $p = 0.00$), and enhanced wellbeing (0.82, $p = 0.00$). The model also indicated that task interdependence predicted psychological capital significantly positively (0.76, $p = 0.00$). This model also showed negative significant impact of the moderating role of task interdependence on the relationship of shared leadership with psychological capital (-0.34, $p = 0.01$).

Figure 4.21

Note: * = $p < 0.05$

Discussion and Conclusion

According to the first hypothesis, organizational commitment was directly linked with shared leadership. The results of the hypothesis ($r = 0.45, p = 0.00$) were significant and a positive relationship between shared leadership and organizational commitment was identified. Similar results were found by Wu & Chen (2018). Studies (Raub & Robert, 2013; Kim et al., 2012; Terzi et al., 2005) have indicated a positive association between shared leadership and organizational commitment. As per the results of SEM shared leadership linked with organizational commitment, direct link having values ($r = 0.54, p = 0.00$) and through mediation of psychological capital having values ($r = 0.12, p = 0.09$). Therefore, the first hypothesis of the study pursues, in direct relation, shared leadership significantly and positively related to the organizational commitment and with mediation effect of psychological capital shared leadership

showed non-significant and had positive association with organizational commitment.

The concept of shared leadership was positively and a significantly related with wellbeing of team has been endorsed and embraced. The results of the hypothesis ($r = 0.39, p = 0.00$) proved the significant and positive relationship between shared leadership and wellbeing. As the findings of the Kevin (2012) shared leadership increase the psychological health of the team which has strong and significant effect on wellbeing of the employees. As per the results of SEM shared leadership had direct link with wellbeing having values ($r = 0.23, p = 0.00$) and through mediation of psychological capital having values ($r = 0.12, p = 0.09$). Therefore, the second hypothesis of the study pursues, in direct relation, shared leadership significantly and positively related to wellbeing and with mediation effect of psychological capital shared leadership showed non-significant and positive association with wellbeing.

According to third hypothesis of the study the mediation of psychological capital was measured. The

results of the hypothesis (correlation SL - PC = 0.39, $p = 0.00$ & correlation PC - OC = 0.28) proved the existence of psychological capital significantly mediates the relationship between shared leadership and organizational commitment. As per the study of Wu & Chen (2018) similar results found that psychological capital mediates the relationship between shared leadership and organizational commitment.

Hence, as per the findings of the results psychological capital mediates the relationship between shared leadership and organizational commitment.

In forth hypothesis of the study the mediation of psychological capital between shared leadership and wellbeing was explored. The results of the hypothesis (correlation SL - PC = 0.39 & correlation PC - WB = 0.54) proved the existence of psychological capital significantly mediates the relationship between shared leadership and wellbeing. As per the findings of Luthans et al., (2008), Avey, (2010) high psychological capital has high psychological tools, which increase the optimistic behavior and had direct impact on wellbeing of the team. Hence, as per the findings of the results, psychological capital mediates the relationship between shared leadership and wellbeing. In this study the moderating effect of task interdependence in projectized organizations (NGO's) was explored, such as if task interdependence is high in Pakistani NGO's then the relationship between shared leadership, organizational commitment and wellbeing would be strengthened. The results of the hypothesis (correlation TI - SL = 0.37 & correlation TI - PC = 0.46) proved the existence of task interdependence significantly moderates the relationship between shared leadership and psychological capital. As per the findings of Molleman, De Jong & Van der Vegt (2007) task interdependence is significantly correlated with environment having shared influence and have direct association with psychological capital. Hollenbeck & Spitzmuller (2012) explored task interdependence has direct association with wellbeing and efficiency, low task interdependence has low efficacy and low wellbeing. Bruke and colleagues (2006) also demonstrated that, team having high task interdependence creates good interaction between team which enhance the organizational commitment of the employees.

But as per the results of SEM full model, where task interdependence used as predictor and moderator the value of the results indicated that task interdependence negatively and significantly moderates the relation between shared leadership and psychological capital. As per the results, individually task interdependence had positive and significant association with shared leadership and psychological capital, but in full model it had negative and significant association as moderator between shared leadership and psychological capital. Hence, as per the findings of the results, task interdependence negatively and significantly moderates the relationship between shared leadership and psychological capital in final model.

Significance of the study

Now a day's project work is focused on innovations with new opportunities. The successful leader actively manages project teams for successful final results. Successful managers communicate with their team through innovative procedures, which include resolving problems, managing those issues and bring new solutions (Schoemaker, Heaton & Teece, 2018). This work will not only provide analytical material for project management but it will also help to understand the needs of the organization to deal with different projects. This study will provide information to help the project managers to utilize and enhance their personal abilities in practicing the shared leadership theory to increase the organizational commitment and wellbeing of the project teams. This research would be useful for project-based organizations to understand the factors that can help enhance the efficiency of the mission and create a positive and safe project atmosphere with a culture of shared leadership in projects. This research would also be useful for researchers to establish strategies that can be used to create an atmosphere that will lead to successful projects for team members.

Research Limitations:

Every research has its limitations so there are some limitations to this research as well. All aspects cannot be addressed in one study. By adding some well-informed literature in this study, few research gaps have been filled in the present analysis. But at the other end, there are several other limits associated

with this research because of time and resource constraints.

- A. The study targeted only Pakistan's project-based organizations (NGO's) and the findings may not be generalized to other sectors.
- B. Due to time constraints, only one mediator and one moderator were checked. Future research should however, extend the model and also check the other mediators. As per the direction of (Rego, Owens et al. 2017) psychological capital can be used as moderator to check the strength of the relationship.
- C. To change the mediation effect of the model, Kayani, Zafar, Aksar & Hassan (2019) suggested emotional execution can be use as mediator to check the wellbeing of the team.
- D. As per recommendation of Nauman Fatima, & Haq (2018) different moderators like organizational justice, emotional intelligence, social support to check the psychological wellbeing and anxiety.
- E. This work only indicates the positive relationship between shared leadership, organizational commitment and wellbeing of team members, but it is also possible to examine negative relationships for more research. This can also be a limitation of this research and can be explored by potential researchers to recognize the negative dimensions of shared leadership, organizational commitment and wellbeing in projects.
- F. In addition, convenience sampling approach is used and select the sample that can easily access and data were collected from limited organizations. So, the findings of the present study cannot be generalized for organizations (NGO's) not participated in this study.

Future Research direction

There are some potential research directions for current research, that have been highlighted and listed below.

- A. Different organization have different corporate and social responsibility This research was limited to Pakistani NGO's, for future research, Cross-industry and inter-industry studies of shared leadership and its impact on organizational commitment and well-being should be analyzed with other related variables. IT/Software industry deals with different projects, so future research IT/Software industry can be used as sample.

- B. Different countries have different values and culture due to social and demographical variation (Patricia M. Greenfield, 2013). This study conducted in the culture of Pakistan and if this same research activity conducted in some other country, it is likely to have different outcomes compared to this study. So, future research can be done some other culture.
- C. The sample size of the current study is slightly small, and it has a significant influence on results of the research. Future research should pick a larger sample size and test the model to be more universal.
- D. Projects are temporary endeavor with specific start and end time having inadequate resources. In development sector, NGO's are working with different projects at the same time, for this complex and multidirectional environment sustainability of employee's creativity and commitment is important. As per the study of Wu Chen (2018) employee's creativity can be measured as dependent variable with organization commitment while shared leadership as independent variable, having mediation of psychological capital.

Implications

There are many implications of the present study that fill the missing gap in literature. This study discussed the role of shared leadership in projectized environment specially NGO sector of Pakistan. This study also addressed how shared leadership effect the organizational commitment of the team and most important psychological wellbeing of the employees, which showed the direct impact of the shared leadership on employees. In this study the mediation effect of psychological capital also checked. which shows the partial mediation between dependent variable (organizational commitment & wellbeing) and independent variable (shared leadership).

To check the strength of the relationship, moderation effect of task interdependence was also checked, but according to results task interdependence showed the negative moderating effect between shared leadership and psychological capital. So, as per results of this study where task interdependence showed negative and significant moderation between shared leadership and psychological capital; will help project managers to understand the connectivity between shared leadership and task interdependence. Whenever task interdependence will increase between the team

members the dependencies of the team member will be low towards the leadership. Which can help project manager to reduce extra work. So, if task interdependence between team members increases, it will decrease the workload on leadership and will also reduce the significance of shared leadership. Therefore, when designing intervention to enhance team productivity, task interdependence must be targeted along with shared leadership.

This study will help project managers/team leads to create shared environment in the organization, which will help to reduce the anxiety and improve the commitment of the team, towards the organization. Project based organizations (NGO's) directly deal different projects at the same time, which create a great pressure on leadership. As per (Gray & Meister, 2004) team having shared environment are less dependent on leader's input. So, this environment will also reduce the extra work and pressure on leadership and empower the project team in their relevant area.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to examine the impact of shared leadership on employee's organizational commitment and wellbeing. Furthermore, this research demonstrates the role of psychological capital as a mediator in the relationship between shared leadership, organizational commitment and employee wellbeing. In addition, this research examined the effect of task interdependence as a moderator between shared leadership and psychological capital. This research focused on Pakistan-based non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and aimed to find empirical evidence of positive shared leadership relationships with employee's organizational commitment and wellbeing. Project High social exchange will decrease the stress of an individual of NGO's are responsible to produce the anticipated results on time, and this study will help managers to manage their team in a better way by improving their shared leadership process, which in effect leads to improved organizational commitment and team's wellbeing in their respective projects. It is also important to examine the various aspects of shared leadership that influence the organizational commitment and wellbeing of the team, that future researchers can take into consideration in relation to specific projects in this

industry. The study also indicated that organizational culture and values play an important role that project managers need to take into consideration, like if managers tend to avoid shared culture in project-based organizations (NGO's), the commitment and wellbeing of the team effect negatively, which can be the reason of project failure. Hence, it can be said that this research offers a comprehensive study that can be followed by the shared leadership of the project managers in carrying out their team's organizational commitment and wellbeing.

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